

INFLUENCE OF VOIDS ON TRANSVERSE CRACK ONSET LOCATION IN CFRP LAMINATES USING X-RAY COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY

Shigeki Aratama^{1,2}, Ryosuke Hashizume², Yusuke Tsumura², Masaaki Nishikawa² and Masaki Hojo²

¹Aerospace Company, Kawasaki Heavy Industries, Ltd.
1, Kawasaki-cho, Kakamigahara, Gifu 504-8710, Japan
Email: aratama_shigeki@khi.co.jp, web page: <https://www.khi.co.jp/>

²Department of Mechanical Engineering and Science, Kyoto University
Building C3, Nishikyo-ku, Kyoto 615-8540, Japan
web page: <http://www.kyoto-u.ac.jp/>

Keywords: CFRP, Strength, Voids, X-ray computed tomography

ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) is now widely used in structural applications, in particular structures for transportation systems like airplanes, due to their high specific strength and stiffness characteristics. Among many forms of its application, CFRP laminates fabricated by stacking prepregs to include multiple fiber directions and curing in autoclave are usually used for high performance components. If curing conditions in CFRP laminate fabrication are not within the specified tolerances, voids can be formed in matrix and result in significant reductions in matrix dominated strengths such as transverse tension, axial compression, flexure and shear.

In this study, tests were performed for more detailed understanding about the effect of voids on matrix dominated strengths using the specimens with intentionally included voids. In addition to the tests for transverse tensile and short beam strengths, in-situ three point bending strength test was performed under observation by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The in-situ test specimens after transverse crack initiation were then observed by X-ray computed tomography (CT) to understand the relationship between the void and the transverse crack onset locations in CFRP laminates.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) is now widely used for the structural components that need both high structural performance and weight reduction. Since CFRP consists of carbon fibers and synthetic polymeric resin, it is an inhomogeneous material having strongly anisotropic mechanical properties such as much higher tensile strength and modulus in fiber direction than those in transverse directions. In the case of CFRP applying epoxy, i.e. typical thermosetting resin for its matrix, it is hence usually used in the form of laminate fabricated by stacking prepregs in a pre-determined arrangement to include intended fiber directions and having resultant material properties as a laminated part. Such CFRP laminates are usually fabricated using an autoclave to apply elevated temperature and pressure conditions specified for the material system to cure the epoxy resin. Temperature condition is to control the chemical reactions of the resin. Pressure condition is to squeeze out excess resin, to consolidate plies, and to minimize the void content. Although there are some causes of void formation like moisture dissolved in resin [1] or air entrapped during lay-up or during impregnation of resin in pre-preg processing [2], many of voids can be eliminated by applying elevated pressures in autoclave, and CFRP laminates can be fabricated with high internal quality.

Even with autoclave curing having such benefits, if curing conditions are not within the specified tolerances in the case like the configuration of the product is complex and pressure conditions cannot be applied properly, voids will be formed in the matrix and hence the matrix dominated strengths such as transverse tension, axial compression, flexure and shear of a CFRP laminate will be significantly reduced [3]. Many of previous researches regarding the effect of voids on the strength of CFRP laminates were focused on the relationship between void volume fraction, V_v , and the strength in

respective fracture modes. Those researches revealed that voids affect mechanical properties of CFRP laminates, such as modulus of elasticity, and degrade compressive strength in fiber direction, tensile and compressive strengths in transverse direction, flexure strength, and interlaminar shear strength [4-10]. It has also been demonstrated that the effect of void on these strength reduction is increased in accordance with increase in V_v . However, the effect of voids on fractures from microscopic viewpoint, e.g. transverse crack initiation as an initial failure of CFRP laminates, has not been well understood. Moreover, many of those works were limited to statistical considerations. Evaluation of void effects on microscale and/or mesoscale would contribute to clear understanding of the mechanics.

In this study, tests were performed for more detailed understanding about the effect of voids on matrix dominated strengths using the specimens with intentionally included voids. In addition to the tests for transverse tensile and short beam strengths, in-situ three point bending strength test was performed under observation by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The in-situ test specimens after transverse crack initiation were then observed by X-ray computed tomography (CT) to understand the relationship between the void and the transverse crack onset locations in CFRP laminates.

2 TESTS FOR MATRIX DOMINATED STRENGTHS

From the previous studies referenced above, voids mainly affect the matrix dominated strengths of CFRP laminates such as transverse tensile and shear strengths so that the tests to investigate the effects of voids on these strengths were performed in this study. In addition, the effect of voids on transverse crack initiation in matrix, i.e. typical initial failure of a CFRP laminate, was investigated by in-situ three point bending test under SEM observation, and those specimens after transverse crack initiation were then observed by CT.

2.1 Materials and specimens

Unidirectional carbon/epoxy UTS50/#135 prepreg (Toho Tenax, 180°C cure type) was used to fabricate the CFRP laminates for the tests performed in this study. The pressure conditions applied in the CFRP laminate fabrication were intentionally changed from the specified one to prepare specimens with respective levels of void volume fractions, V_v . Stacking sequences were unidirectional $[0_{24}]$ for the transverse tensile and shear strength tests and cross-ply $[90_2/0_5]_s$, i.e. consisted of internal 0° layers and a few 90° layers placed on both surfaces, for the in-situ three point bending test. Ultrasonic inspection was performed to check if voids were uniformly distributed at a macroscopic scale in each laminate. Specimens for the respective tests were cut out from these laminates.

2.2 Transverse tensile strength test

Figure 1 shows the outline of the specimen for the transverse tensile strength (TTS) test in this study. Totally seven CFRP laminates with V_v of 0, 1.0, 2.1, 2.7, 3.1, 4.6, and 7.1% were prepared for this test in the way described in 2.1. The V_v was evaluated by optical microscope observation as the ratio of the cumulative area of voids to the area of the representative cut surface. Four specimens of 25mm width and 175mm length were cut out from each laminate including respective levels of voids. Test was performed in accordance with ASTM D3039 with 1mm/min crosshead speed. The applied load and displacement from testing machine and the output from biaxial strain gages installed on both sides of a specimen were recorded.

2.3 Short beam strength test

Short beam strength tests in accordance with ASTM D2344 were performed to evaluate the interlaminar shear strengths (ILSS) of the specimens with or without voids. Figure 2 shows the outline of the specimens and test configuration. Four specimens were cut out from each of the same seven CFRP laminates as the TTS test. The void volume fractions of the specimens in this test were therefore also 0.0, 1.0, 2.1, 2.7, 3.1, 4.6, and 7.1%. The width and length of a specimen were determined in accordance with the test specification based on the actual thickness of the respective laminates. The crosshead speed was 1.27 mm/min and the applied load from testing machine was recorded.

Figure 1: Outline of specimen for transverse tensile strength test.

Figure 2: Outline of specimen and test configuration for short-beam strength test.

2.4 In-situ three point bending test under SEM observation

In-situ three point bending test was performed under SEM observation using the loading apparatus shown in Figure 3 installed in SEM (JSM-6510, JEOL). This loading apparatus was exactly the same one used in the tests performed by Hobbiebrunken, et al [11]. As shown in Figure 4, specimen was supported by two supporting pins, and three point bending load was applied by the loading pin at the center. The diameters of the support and loading pins were 6mm and the distances between those pins were 10mm.

Figure 3: Loading apparatus installed in SEM.

Figure 4: Geometry of specimen for in-situ three point bending test in SEM.

The cross-ply stacking sequence $[90_2/0_5]_s$, specially arranged for this case, had an advantage that enabled observation of transverse crack initiation in the longitudinal center area under transverse tensile stress condition while preventing sudden final failure of specimens by supporting most of the applied load by 0° layers and limiting the displacement. Specimens of three levels of V_v , 0%, 2% and 4.6%, were prepared as described in 2.1 and named as Specimen A, B and C, respectively. The dimensions of the specimens were 30mm length and 3mm width. The surface of each test specimen for SEM observation was prepared by three steps of mirror polish, flattening, intermediate and final polishing using polisher (ECOMET3, BUEHLER), and finally 30-second gold deposition was applied by an ion coater (FINECOATER JFC-1200, Japan Electron Optics Laboratory (JEOL)).

The displacement of the loading pin was manually controlled and the applied load was measured using a load cell with a capacity of 2kN. The load cell was connected to a signal conditioner (CDV-700A, Kyowa Electronic Instruments) and the voltage output was recorded using data acquisition software (PCD-320A, Kyowa Electronic Instruments). The loads were recorded at the times when the transverse cracks (up to two or three cracks) were observed in the in-situ SEM image. Those obtained loads corresponding to the respective void volume fractions were compared to investigate the effects of voids.

2.5 CT observation of specimens after in-situ three point bending test in SEM

The specimens after the in-situ three point bending test (i.e. after transverse cracks initiation) were observed by CT to understand the relationship between the transverse crack onset locations and the spatial distributions and/or the morphological features of voids in CFRP laminates.

X-ray images were taken with high-resolution micro-CT scanner system (SkyScan 1172, Bruker) at 100kV source voltage and $41\mu\text{A}$ source current. The size of a scanned image was 1000 by 668 pixels. The resolutions were set to 5.15 and $4.88\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ for the specimens of void volume fractions of 2.0% and 4.6%, respectively, to observe the region including transverse cracks in a specimen. The rotation step between the scans was 0.2deg and hence total of 1800 images were taken for a set of 360deg scans. Solution of zinc iodide (ZI) was penetrated into the transverse cracks before scanning to improve their contrast in X-ray image.

Image reconstruction program (SkyScan NRecon package, Bruker) was used to reconstruct cross-section images from cone-beam projections using implemented Feldkamp algorithm. Threshold grey levels were adjusted to clearly identify the voids and transverse cracks (ZI penetrated) in each specimen. The region of interest, i.e. the region of specimen in this observation, was extracted from the reconstructed 3-D cylindrical shaped images. The reconstructed CT images were evaluated using the viewer program (DATAVIEWER, Bruker).

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Transverse tensile strength

Figure 5 shows the transverse tensile strength (TTS) and modulus versus void volume fraction, V_v , obtained from TTS test. The TTS and modulus were normalized using the respective averages of the test results for the specimens of $V_v=0\%$. The coefficients of variation (CV) of TTS and modulus were also plotted on this figure.

In Figure 5, the reduction in TTS was nearly 30% for the largest void volume fractions, $V_v=7.1\%$, while the reduction in modulus was within around 10% even for the same V_v . The CV of TTS was much larger than that of modulus for almost all range of V_v . In addition, it varied greatly from below 2% at $V_v=3.1\%$ to over 7% at $V_v=2.1\%$ and it was around 6% even at $V_v=0\%$. Thus no clear relationship was observed between V_v and the CV of TTS. In contrast to the CV of TTS, the CV of modulus was low for the most of the range of V_v and seemed to have a tendency to slightly increase with the increase in V_v .

3.2 Short beam strength

Figure 6 shows the ILSS versus V_v from the short beam strength test with TTS test results shown in the previous section. Similarly to Figure 5, strengths were normalized using the averages of the results

for the specimens of $V_v=0\%$. The CV of ILSS and TTS were also plotted on this figure.

It was understood from Figure 6 that the reductions in ILSS and TTS were very similar to each other, and the reduction of ILSS was also nearly 30% for $V_v=7.1\%$, which was at the level similar to the reduction in TTS. The CV of ILSS was mostly at low level compared to that of TTS for all ranges of V_v , as it was well below 2% even at $V_v=7.1\%$. It also seemed to have a tendency to slightly increase with the increase in V_v .

Figure 5: Transverse tensile strength (TTS) and coefficient of variation (CV) vs. void volume fractions.

Figure 6: Interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) and CV vs. void volume fractions (with TTS results).

3.3 In-situ three point bending test under SEM observation

Macroscopic strains at the transverse crack initiation (initial failure strains) in the in-situ three point bending test under SEM observation for the respective V_v are shown in Figure 7. The average initial failure strains of Specimens B and C were 68% and 50%, respectively, of that of Specimen A. It was thus confirmed that the void volume fractions, V_v , significantly affect the transverse crack initiation. Considering this initial failure strain as the transverse strength, this tendency of reducing initial failure strains with increase in V_v , was similar to the ones in the previous studies [5, 6]. The ratios of strength reductions in Figure 7 were, however, much larger than those in these previous studies.

Figure 7: Strains at the first transverse crack initiation in in-situ three point bending test.

3.4 CT of specimens after in-situ three point bending test in SEM

Figure 8 is an example of the typical cross-sectional images from the CT of specimens after the in-situ three point bending test. Voids were seen as circular or cluster of circular shape in 90° layers and thin long shape in 0° layers in this image. Transverse cracks observed in 90° layers at tensile loading side of the specimen ran through the voids, and they went into the voids at the void edges located transversely to the loading direction. These transverse cracks and voids in 90° layers were observed at similar location in many cross-sectional images parallel to the plane of paper. Moreover, even in the cross-sectional images that voids were vanished, these transverse cracks tended to run at the locations similar to this image. Based on these observations, it was suggested that two dimensional stress conditions could be assumed in the 90° layers at the tensile side of these specimens.

Figure 8: Example of cross-sectional image from X-ray computed tomography (CT) showing transverse cracks running through the voids in a CFRP laminate.

4 DISCUSSION

Figure 9 shows the failure loads versus V_v from the TTS and ILSS tests. Not the averages of the failure loads but the respective failure loads for all of the four specimens for a V_v were plotted. These loads were again normalized using the averages of respective failure loads for the specimens of $V_v=0\%$. The tendencies to decrease in failure loads with increase in V_v , were similar to each other for TTS and

ILSS tests. The variations of failure loads for a V_v for TTS and ILSS tests seemed to have a tendency to decrease with increase in V_v , and those tendencies were also similar to each other. However, the CV of TTS shown in Figures 5 and 6 varied greatly and had larger values compared to that of ILSS. This can be understood as the voids affect these strengths in a different way, but the resultant effects of voids on these strengths were at similar levels to each other. However, based on the difference in CV, TTS seemed to have a tendency to be more affected by the void locations or distributions compared to ILSS. This means if a void location, in combination with void morphology in some case, is critical to TTS, TTS will be greatly reduced and vice versa.

For detailed explanation about such effect of voids on TTS, Figure 10 shows a typical example of microscopic strain distributions in 90° layers of CFRP laminates including voids. This distribution was calculated by image analysis on the SEM images of 90° layers at the tensile side obtained in in-situ three point bending tests [12]. In this result, strain concentrations were actually observed around some of the voids, even though no apparent strain concentrations were observed around the other voids. These observations suggested that voids basically caused strain concentrations around them and resulted in the reduction of TTS, while the levels of those effects would depend on the void locations, morphologies or the combinations of both.

Figure 9: Failure loads vs. void volume fractions from transverse tensile and short beam tests.

Figure 10: Example of microscopic distributions of tensile strain ϵ_{22} in 90° layers of CFRP laminates with intentionally included voids (Specimen C ($V_v=4.6\%$) at $F=2.0 \times 10^2$ N).

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the effect of voids on matrix dominated strengths and mechanical properties of CFRP laminates were experimentally investigated by TTS and ILSS tests and in-situ three point bending test under SEM observation. Based these results, it was understood that TTS might be greatly reduced if void existed at locations critical to the strength. On the other hand, transverse tensile modulus and ILSS might be less affected by the locations and spatial distributions of voids.

In-situ three point bending test in SEM showed reductions in the strains at the transverse crack initiation, and the reduction was much larger than the strength reductions for TTS and ILSS above.

CT was very effective tool to observe the internal conditions of in-situ three point bending test specimens. Similar CT observations will therefore be applied to the specimens of the other tests for more investigation about the mechanics of the CFRP laminates including voids.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to express their sincere thanks to Professor Takushi Miyake, Mr Kazuya Takenaka, and Division of Instrumental Analysis, Gifu University, for their assistance in the observations with X-ray computed tomography.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. K. Grunenfelder and S. R. Nutt, Void formation in composite prepregs - effect of dissolved moisture, *Composites Science and Technology*, **70**, 2010, pp. 2304-2309.
- [2] S. S. Tavares, V. Michaud & J.-A. E. Månson, Through thickness air permeability of prepregs during cure, *Composites: Part A*, **40**, 2009, pp. 1587-1596.
- [3] J. M. Tang, W. I. Lee and G. S. Springer, Effects of Cure Pressure on Resin Flow, Voids, and Mechanical Properties, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **21**, 1987, pp. 421-440.
- [4] B. D. Harper, G. H. Staab and R. S. Chen, A note on the effects of voids upon the hygral and mechanical properties of AS4/3502 graphite/epoxy, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **21**, 1987, pp. 280-289.
- [5] P. Olivier, J. P. Cottu and B. Ferret, Effects of cure cycle pressure and voids on some mechanical properties of carbon/epoxy laminates, *Composites*, **26**(7), 1995, pp. 509-515.
- [6] L. Ye, K. Friedrich, J. Kästel and Y.-W. Mai, Consolidation of unidirectional CF/PEEK composites from commingled yarn prepreg, *Composites Science and Technology*, **54**, 1995, pp. 349-358.
- [7] N. L. Hancox, The compression strength of unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced plastic, *Journal of Materials Science*, **10**, 1975, pp. 234-242.
- [8] N. L. Hancox, The effects of flaws and voids on the shear properties of CFRP, *Journal of Materials Science*, **12**, 1977, pp. 884-892.
- [9] S. Hernández, F. Sket, J. M. Molina-Aldareguía, C. González and J. LLorca, Effect of curing cycle on void distribution and interlaminar shear strength in polymer-matrix composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **71**, 2011, pp. 1331-1341.
- [10] R. Talreja and C. V. Singh, *Damage and Failure of Composite Materials*, Cambridge University Press, 2012.
- [11] T. Hobbiebrunken, M. Hojo, T. Adachi, C. De Jong and B. Fiedler, Evaluation of interfacial strength in CF/epoxies using FEM and in-situ experiments, *Composites: Part A*, **37**, 2006, pp. 2248-2256.
- [12] Y. Tsumura, S. Aratama, M. Nishikawa and M. Hojo, Development of a Fiber Location Search Based Image Analysis Method for Transverse Strain Distribution Measurement in CFRP Laminate, *Journal of the Japan Society for Composite Materials*, **40**(2), 2014, pp.71-80 (in Japanese)